

Developing a Conducive Learning Environment for Children with Intellectual & Developmental Disabilities: A Responsibility of Special Education Teachers

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ABSTRACT: A conducive learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs) is essential for fostering adaptive behavior and meaningful educational outcomes. A quantitative descriptive design was employed, and data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to (N=130) special education teachers working in the Punjab government and private sector. Purposive sampling technique was employed by the researchers in this study. Statistical analysis through SPSS version 23 revealed that respondents strongly affirmed the importance of the teacher–student relationship in fostering a conducive learning environment ($M = 4.30$, $SD = .82$), and also highlighted the effectiveness of diverse teaching aids, including assistive technology, in supporting children with IDD ($M = 4.05$, $SD = .97$).

This study recommends that to guarantee accessibility and engagement for all students with IDD, schools place a high priority on enhancing the relationship dynamics between teachers and students through continual professional development.

Key words: Intellectual Disabilities, Conducive Learning Environment, Special Education, Teachers, Classrooms.

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1. Introduction

For children with ID to function at their best, attain personal autonomy, and feel satisfied with their life, they need education, community involvement, freedom from

discrimination, social security, healthcare, family support, and more equitable interactions within the legal system. A setting that encourages successful learning by giving students safety, comfort, and involvement is known as a conducive learning environment. The physical, emotional, and social aspects of this setting all work together to improve the learning process. A conducive learning environment provides students with safety, comfort, and engagement to promote successful learning. This environment's social, emotional, and physical components all contribute to a better learning experience. A supportive learning environment significantly impacts students' academic achievement and overall development. An orderly learning environment improves motivation, engagement, and the educational experience as a whole. Students' academic performance can be enhanced by fostering interest in them through the use of continuous practices that highlight the intellectual components of learning (Ali et al., 2024). The most important factor in a child's learning is a supportive classroom environment. Students' interaction with their teachers affects their development on the intellectual and personal levels (Almalki, 2024). To improve the overall quality of education, educational environments for children with special needs place a strong emphasis on their roles in implementing effective plans and techniques to assist those with intellectual and developmental disabilities (Ritonga & Wati, 2024). To effectively help students with intellectual and developmental disabilities, they must also work with parents and participate in ongoing professional development (Damyantov, 2024). Students with intellectual disabilities show a propensity for structured activities and open spaces, a variety of behavioral patterns, poor social participation outcomes, unfavorable peer relationships, and disparities in social self-perception (Wang et al., 2025).

Statement of the Problem

Children with intellectual disabilities need a supportive, well-organized learning environment that meets their specific needs to effectively handle these difficulties. This study seeks to explore the critical role of the special education teacher in developing conducive learning environments for children with IDD, identifying the barriers they face and the strategies they employ to enhance student engagement, safety, and learning outcomes. Regarding special education teachers, in particular, there is a significant gap in developing a conducive environment in the class for children with IDD. The usefulness of creating a conducive environment in classroom settings has not been thoroughly

studied; thus, special education teachers may have trouble developing a conducive environment to enhance learners' learning and engagement.

Objectives of the Research

The objectives of the study were to:

- Find out the teachers' perception about existing practices of conducive learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities as per their demographics, i.e, gender, experience, and school level.
- Analyze the effectiveness of a conducive learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities in special education schools.
- Identify the key components of a conducive learning environment for children with IDD.

- Explore the challenges faced by teachers in developing conducive learning environments.
- Highlight the efforts delineated by teachers to develop a conducive learning environment for children with ID in school.

Research Questions

The following were the questions of the research:

1. What is the teachers' perception about existing practices of conducive learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities as per their demographics, i.e, gender, experience, and school level?
2. What is the effectiveness of a conducive learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities in special education schools?
3. What are the key components of a conducive learning environment for children with IDD?
4. What are the challenges faced by teachers in developing a conducive learning environment?
5. What are the efforts delineated by teachers to develop a conducive learning environment for children with ID in school?

Significance of the study

A conducive learning environment is a setting that allows for the free exchange of ideas, thoughts, and skills among teachers and learners, enabling them to achieve the expected educational goals while considering the physical, psychological, social, and cultural needs of all learners. This study can inform teachers that a conducive environment plays an essential role in students' learning. This study may help to find a successful, conducive environment that improves student participation, engagement, and performance, which will be beneficial for all aspects of a child's development. This study seeks to advance integration and accessibility in the learning environment. This study can help to create a more advanced and supportive environment for every learner by using the successful strategies of a conducive environment. This study will add to the broader body of research in the special education sector. It will lay the groundwork for further analysis and promote continuous discussion in a conducive environment on successful teaching strategies in various educational contexts by addressing the current gap in the literature.

Limitations of the Research

Limitations of this research were:

1. The study was limited to the province of Punjab only. Therefore, the findings of this research may not be generalized to the other provinces of Pakistan.
2. The data were collected through a self-developed structured questionnaire, which may be subject to response bias and social desirability effects.
3. The sample size is limited to 130 teachers, which may restrict the broader generalization of the results.
4. The study employed a quantitative and descriptive research design; in-depth qualitative insights into teachers' experiences and practices could not be explored.

De-Limitations of the Research

This research was delimited to:

1. Only the teachers of children with intellectual disabilities were included in the study. Teachers working with autistic children were not included in the study, as their schools in the province of Punjab have a distinct identity.
2. The sample has restrictions to the teachers working in the public-private special education of the province of Punjab only.
3. This study was delimited to collect the teachers' perception about effectiveness, challenges, and efforts related to the conducive learning environment for children with ID.
4. The researchers developed a structured questionnaire as a data collection instrument for this study.

2. Literature Review

Intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD) are conditions that considerably impede both intellectual ability and adaptive behaviors, and they typically start before the age of 22 (Rao et al., 2025). Through efficient physical environment management, maintaining cleanliness and sufficient facilities, and cultivating positive interpersonal relationships among teachers, students, and parents, the school promotes a favorable learning environment that boosts student motivation and achievement (Ruwaitah et al., 2025). A favorable learning environment is achieved by making sure there are sufficient physical facilities, creating a peaceful social environment, and offering academic assistance through activities and supervision, all of which improve students' motivation, focus, and overall learning accomplishment (Aziz & Riyanto, 2025). Effective classroom management, student-teacher collaboration, and extracurricular activities improve student involvement and foster their intellectual, social, and emotional growth (Febriani et al., 2025). The school contributes by establishing a welcoming atmosphere with all-conducive amenities like labs and reading nooks, as well as by encouraging positive teacher-student interactions that boost students' drive and inventiveness and ultimately result in better learning outcomes (Pratama et al., 2025; Joshi, 2025). Schools help by fostering a supportive, safe environment that fosters both academic achievement and emotional development. Establishing positive communication, encouraging respect for one another, and building a supportive relationship with students are all part of the teacher's job in a conducive learning environment. This harmony fosters effective learning by improving social relationships, classroom management, and students' sense of safety (Nurdalia, 2025; Hardivizon & Salma, 2025). Furthermore, increasing public knowledge of the difficulties these children encounter can create a more encouraging environment, which will ultimately benefit their general growth and well-being (Bhatia & Kour, 2025). In a conducive learning environment, the teacher's responsibility is to facilitate, motivate, and assist students while fostering an enjoyable, meaningful, and communicative environment. They modify tactics based on the traits of the students, guaranteeing active participation to improve learning satisfaction and academic results (Tasya'ah et al., 2025). For teachers to provide a supportive, creative, and quality-focused learning environment, teachers are essential. In addition to teaching, teachers also serve as facilitators, motivators, and skill developers for their students. Additionally, instructors' proficiency with a range of media, learning methodologies, and continuous professional development helps to raise the

standard of education (Supriatna et al., 2026). In order to satisfy the different requirements of students, the conversation highlights the significance of professional development, cultural competency, and adaptation (Zaripova, 2025). Positive teacher–learner interactions, a conducive classroom climate, effective classroom organization, and the availability of instructional resources were identified as key features. Additionally, it was discovered that teachers commonly used innovative teaching techniques, especially differentiated education, technology-enhanced instruction, collaborative learning, and creative teaching methods. Academic behavior was well graded in terms of learner outcomes, with students exhibiting great attention, active involvement, peer cooperation, and obedience to classroom regulations (Cordova, 2026).

3. Methodology

Research Design

This research study was quantitative research, which was descriptive in nature.

Population of the Study

The teachers of intellectual and developmental disabilities are the respondents of the study from the special education department of Punjab. The majority of teachers belong to the government sector (82.3%), while the rest of the respondents belong to the private sector.

Sample & Sampling Technique

The respondents of the study were teachers (N=130) from the field of intellectual and developmental disabilities, using a purposive sampling technique. The majority, 66.2% of respondents, were females. The age of the respondents ranged from 21 years to above 41 years, with the majority falling between 21 and 40 years. The majority of the respondents were B.Ed special education qualified. The majority, 80.0% of respondents, received training in the field of IDD. Respondents were drawn from a wide range of cities in Punjab, with the largest proportion from **Lahore (N=56)**. Other cities represented included Okara (N=6), Gujranwala (N=4), Faisalabad (N=4), Multan (N=4), Jhang (N=4), Kasur (N = 4), Sargodha (N = 4), Bhakkar(N= 3), Hafizabad (N=2), Rawalpindi (N=2), Chakwal (N=2), Bahawalpur (N=2), Sahiwal (N=2), Burewala (N=2), Mianwali (N=2), Pattoki (N=1), Layyah (N=1), Bahawalnagar (N=1), DG Khan (N=3), Chunian (N=2), Pakpattan (N = 2), Haroonabad (N=2), Lodhran (N=2), Khushab (N=2), Nankana Sahib (N=2), and Sheikhpura (N= 2).

This distribution highlights that while Lahore contributed the majority of respondents, the respondents were geographically diverse, covering both urban and semi-urban districts across Punjab.

Table 1: Demographic Details of Respondents

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	30%
Female	91	70%
JSET	60	46%
SSET	29	22%
Others	41	32%
21–30 years	55	42%

31–40 years	62	48%
41 years & above	13	10%
B.Ed (Hons)/BS/M.A./M.Ed	86	66%
MS/M.Phil	39	30%
PhD	10	8%
1–5 years of experience	64	49%
6–10 years of experience	21	16%
11–15 years of experience	27	21%
16+ years of experience	18	14%
Special Education Centers	97	75%
Schools for IDD's	33	25%
Public institutions	106	82%
Private institutions	24	18%
Received training	105	81%
No training	25	19%

Research instrument

The researchers used a self-developed structured questionnaire to collect the data. The research instrument consisted of two parts. First part consisted of demographic information of respondents, such as gender, age, experience, qualification, designation, school type, sector, and training.

Second part of questionnaire consisted of 37 closed-ended items on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. After that, researchers administered research tool to collect relevant data from 130 teachers of intellectual and developmental disabilities from public & private sectors across Punjab province.

Validity & Reliability of Study's Instrument

The validity of the instrument was assured through the opinion of field experts (N = 03). However, reliability of the research instrument was assessed through SPSS software **Cronbach's Alpha** 0.763.

Data collection

Data for this study were collected online using a self-developed questionnaire distributed through digital platforms by using a survey method approach. The questionnaire link was shared with teachers of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities working in both government and private sector institutions across Punjab. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and assured of confidentiality before completing the instrument. Participation was voluntary, and teachers were able to access and submit the questionnaire at their convenience.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data from the respondents were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were employed to summarize demographic variables and responses to questionnaire items. Inferential statistical techniques were also applied to explore relationships among variables. Independent respondents' t-tests were

conducted to examine differences between groups (e.g., public vs. private sector teachers), while Pearson correlation analysis was used to identify associations between teachers' practices and perceived effectiveness of conducive learning environments. Results were converted into numeric outputs.

Ethical consideration for the study

The ethical considerations for the study were compiled strictly and properly. The respondents were informed earlier before being asked for personal information. They were also assured that the information from them would not be revealed in the future by their names. But the information gathered from them will only be used for the research purpose.

Quantitative Data Analysis

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16+ years of experience	18	14%
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Table 2: Statements with Descriptive Statistics

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation
The current learning environment in special education schools is effective for children with IDD.	3.2154	1.04906
The school administration provides adequate support to maintain a conducive learning environment	3.4385	.89792
My school provides sufficient sensory-friendly resources, including lighting and noise control in classrooms for students with IDD.	3.3385	1.01580
The existing physical infrastructure fulfils the learning needs of children with IDD through a conducive learning environment.	3.1692	1.07212
My classroom layout is appropriate for the mobility and safety needs of children with IDD.	3.5462	1.01242
My colleagues are helpful to me in maintaining a conducive learning environment for children with IDD.	3.7385	1.00042
Children with IDD show improved learning outcomes in a conducive learning environment.	3.7077	2.00946
A conducive learning environment helps children with IDD improve their communication skills.	3.6308	.84577
A positive, conducive learning environment reduces behavioral issues in children with IDD.	3.3231	.89109
Children with IDD demonstrate better social skills in a conducive learning environment.	3.5769	.87926
A conducive learning environment helps in emotional well-being through students' engagement & interaction.	3.5923	.79432
A conducive learning environment improves the students' learning about daily living skills	3.9231	.80324
The learning environment is physically comfortable and promotes active learning	3.7462	.88319
Minimal distractions in the classroom increase the effectiveness of a conducive learning environment	3.9385	.86045
Teaching materials and learning resources are available and accessible.	3.5538	.89842
The teacher fosters a respectful and supportive classroom culture through task analysis.	3.7769	.90875
Classroom design supports active engagement of children with IDD.	3.8692	.80105
Visual aids and instructional materials are important components of the learning environment for children with IDD	4.2923	2.75469
The classroom must have a positive and supportive atmosphere for children with IDD.	4.5615	3.64937
Adequate physical space is important for children with IDD to move around and engage in activities.	4.1462	.86366

The teacher-student relationship is essential for a conducive learning environment.	4.3000	.82264
Flexible and adaptable teaching strategies with reinforcement are necessary for children with IDD.	4.1538	.87570
Explicit and structured routines are essential for children with IDD in the classroom	4.0154	.68182
I find it difficult to provide individualized instruction due to limited resources.	4.1385	3.66368
I feel difficulty in maintaining discipline in the classroom for children with IDD.	3.5385	1.01274
The lack of support staff makes it difficult to create a conducive learning environment for children with IDD.	3.9000	.90520
Training opportunities are insufficient for teachers in creating an effective, conducive learning environment for children with IDD.	3.7615	.92178
Time constraints make it difficult to implement individualized learning strategies for children with IDD.	4.0308	2.70784
The physical classroom environment is lacking peer support for children with IDD.	3.8000	1.10250
The lack of collaboration among teachers and other professionals hinders the maintenance conducive learning environment.	3.7154	.97436
I face challenges due to a lack of collaboration with the families of children with IDD.	3.6154	1.02212
I regularly adapt my teaching methods to meet the needs of children with IDD.	3.9231	.94513
I collaborate with other teachers and professionals to improve the learning environment for children with IDD	3.9385	1.02491
I actively seek professional development opportunities to improve my skills in creating a conducive learning environment.	4.1154	.86835
I create a welcoming and supportive classroom atmosphere for children with IDD.	4.0846	1.01183
I use various teaching aids (visual, auditory, and kinesthetic), including assistive technology, to support children with IDD.	4.0538	.96699
I provide one-on-one support for children with IDD when needed.	4.1692	.82723

Table 2 depicts the quantitative data analysis processed through descriptive statistics with their mean and standard deviation (SD). The highest mean value is = **4.5615** and standard deviation (S.D) **3.64937** which is related to the statement that the classroom must have a positive and supportive atmosphere for children with IDD, And the lowest mean value is 3.1692 and standard deviation (S.D) **1.07212** which is related to the statement that the existing physical infrastructure fulfils the learning needs of children with IDD through a conducive learning environment.

Table 3: t-test

Independent T-Test Administration on the Gender of Teachers of Intellectually and Developmentally Disabled Children.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	F	Std. Error Mean	Sig.
Male	44	2.3750	1.30247	2.406	13	.51219	.032
Female	86	1.1429	.37796	2.556	8.322	.48214	.033

Table 3 presents the results of the independent respondents' t-test comparing the means of statistics related to a conducive learning environment between genders, i.e., male and female. There was a crucial variance in the score for the conducive learning environment of male ($M=2.3750$, $SD=1.30247$) and the conducive environment for female ($M=1.1429$, $SD=.37796$) condition; $t(13) = 2.406$, $p=.032$.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA

One-Way ANOVA on the Effectiveness of the Current Learning Environment in Special Education Schools for Children with IDD, as Per Teachers' Experiences.

	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.811	4	.703	.532	.713
Within Groups	165.158	125	1.321		
Total	167.969	129			

This table displays the results of the ANOVA test for developing a conducive learning environment for children with Idd, specifically the Responsibility of the special education teacher. The result of the ANOVA test did not show a significant difference at the alpha level.05, $F(4,125) = .523$, $p = .713$.

Major Findings:

Followings are the major findings of the study. These findings include the frequencies of the demographics of the respondents, their responses resulted through the administration of descriptive statistics, and the results of inferential statistics. These are the most relevant findings that address the research questions:

1. The majority, 66.2% of respondents, were female.
2. Less than half, 48.5% of respondents have experience of 1-5 years.
3. The majority of respondents, 52.3%, who agree are aged 31-40 years.
4. The majority, 65.4% of respondents, agree as per their Qualification, which is B.Ed. Hons/BS/M.A./M. Ed
5. The majority, 80.0% of respondents, received training in the field of IDD.

6. The majority, 76.2% of respondents, have a special education center as their school type.
7. The majority, 82.3% of respondents, belonged to the public sector.
8. Less than half, 46.2% of respondents, have the designation of JSET.
9. The descriptive analysis indicates that respondents generally perceive the learning environment in special education schools as moderately effective for children with IDD, as reflected by a mean score of 3.21 (SD = 1.04), suggesting a satisfactory but improvable situation.
10. The descriptive analysis indicates that respondents generally perceive a positive, conducive learning environment as effective in reducing behavioral issues among children with IDD, as reflected by a mean score of 3.32 (SD = .89), suggesting that supportive classroom conditions play a meaningful role in minimizing behavioral challenges.
11. The descriptive analysis indicates that respondents generally perceive teachers as fostering a respectful and supportive classroom culture through the use of task analysis, as reflected by a mean score of 3.78 (SD = .91), suggesting that instructional strategies grounded in task analysis are viewed as effective in promoting positive classroom dynamics for children with IDD.
12. The descriptive analysis indicates that respondents strongly affirm the importance of the teacher–student relationship in creating a conducive learning environment, as reflected by a mean score of 4.30 (SD = .82), suggesting that positive relational dynamics between teachers and students are perceived as a critical factor in fostering effective learning for children with IDD.
13. School administration support was rated relatively high (M = 3.43, SD = .89), indicating that most respondents believe administrative efforts contribute positively to maintaining a conducive learning environment.
14. The availability of sensory-friendly resources, such as appropriate lighting and noise control, also received a moderate rating (M = 3.33, SD = 1.01), indicating partial provision of sensory accommodations for students with IDD.
15. The descriptive analysis indicates that respondents generally affirm the use of diverse teaching aids—including visual, auditory, kinesthetic methods, and assistive technology—as supportive for children with IDD, as reflected by a mean score of 4.05 (SD = .97), suggesting that multimodal instructional strategies are perceived as effective in enhancing learning experiences and accessibility.
16. The results of the independent t-test indicate that there is no crucial difference in the scores of female teachers of children with IDD and male teachers of children with IDD.
17. The ANOVA test results showed that there was no major difference in the current learning environment in special education schools, which is effective for children with IDD, as per the experiences of teachers.

4. Discussion

Many elements play a role in creating a helpful learning environment for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities. One of the essential elements that significantly impacts the overall development of individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities is a supportive learning environment. Many factors influence the creation of an atmosphere

that is conducive to learning for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities. A supportive learning environment is one of these essential elements and has a significant impact on the overall development of individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities. Teachers can also apply Universal Design principles, such as equitable, flexible, simple, and intuitive use; palpable information; error tolerance; and minimal physical effort, to create materials that are physically accessible to all (Evans et al., 2023). The current learning environment in special education schools is effective for children with IDD. This indicates that nearly half of the respondents perceive existing practices as supportive, though effectiveness is not universal.

Additionally, conducive learning environments have a critical role in influencing how students view their peers who have IDD. Additionally, it is essential to look at how these students' self-concept is affected by their motor and physical skills (Schluchter et al., 2023). A significant number of teachers reported that time constraints hinder the implementation of individualized learning strategies. This finding highlights a systemic challenge in special education, where teachers often struggle to balance workload with individualized instruction. (Ruteere et al., 2021) Also noted that teacher workload and leadership structures affect the implementation of adaptive strategies. Trained teaching staff and professional support improved the functioning and academic skills of children with IDD.

The study revealed that teachers face challenges due to a lack of collaboration with families of children with IDDs. This finding underscores the importance of family-school partnerships in fostering student success (Goodwin & Long, 2023) found that parental perceptions of culturally responsive teaching directly influence children's mental health and well-being. Students' attitudes and behaviors can be positively shaped by a supportive and well-run school environment. Teaching methods, including collaborative learning exercises and flipped classrooms, are investigated as successful ways to enhance communication skills (Borasheva, 2024). active learning strategies such as think-pair-share (TPS), problem-based learning (PBL), flipped classrooms, and collaborative projects are essential for promoting student engagement, critical thinking, and academic success. Children with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities (IDD) encounter difficulties in learning functional skills because of cognitive impairment and working memory deficits (Entrich, 2021).

According to the findings of this study, teachers strongly agreed that they create welcoming and supportive classroom atmospheres for children with IDDs. This reflects teachers' commitment to inclusion and positive classroom culture. It demonstrated that supportive environments improve self-concept and physical engagement for children with intellectual disabilities. Some obstacles in the implementation of classroom management include low student awareness of learning responsibilities and the existence of disruptive extracurricular activities. It was concluded in the study that good classroom management plays an important role in creating a conducive learning atmosphere and increasing student motivation (Abidin & Muhammad, 2024). The learning environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' learning outcomes, attitudes, and behaviors. A positive and supportive learning environment can enhance students' motivation, engagement, and achievement, while a negative or unsupportive environment can hinder their learning and well-being.

This study revealed that teachers foster respectful and supportive classroom cultures through task analysis. Task analysis is a structured instructional strategy that breaks down complex tasks into manageable steps, thereby promoting clarity and respect in learning.

(Kubiak et al., 2021) emphasized that structured approaches enhance self-determination and confidence among students with intellectual disabilities. This finding confirms that task analysis is not only an instructional tool but also a means of cultivating respect and trust in classrooms. Developing successful ways to support students with ID might be aided by understanding the lived experiences of their parents. Collaborative education is a dynamic process of interaction between educators and students as well as between students themselves. It involves the verbal and nonverbal exchange of information, thoughts, and feelings (Pattiasina et al., 2025).

The results showed teachers endorsed a positive, conducive learning environment that reduces barriers to learning. This finding aligns with (Amali et al., 2023), who argued that supportive environments improve motivation and reduce behavioral challenges. It was further discovered through this study that the teacher–student relationship is essential for a conducive learning environment. This finding reinforces the importance of interpersonal connections in special education. (Williams et al., 2022) highlighted the role of relationships in fostering social inclusion and emotional well-being. The consistency between this study and prior literature confirms that strong teacher–student bonds are foundational to both academic success and social development.

In the next findings, teachers reported using various teaching aids, including visual, auditory, and kinesthetic tools, and assistive technology, to support children with IDD. This finding demonstrates teachers' efforts to integrate diverse resources into instruction. (Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023) emphasized the importance of differentiated resources and assistive tools in education for children with special needs. The adoption of teaching aids and technology in this study reflects a growing trend toward resource-based inclusion, though further training and investment are needed to expand their use. Teachers' capacity to regulate learning in the classroom affects the high degree of students' creativity.

5. Conclusion

The several responsibilities that teachers are primarily responsible for include lesson design, lesson execution, an additional task allocated by the administration, creating an IEP for the child's current academic achievement level, and increasing functional abilities. The results of the study, the methodology employed, and the pertinent literature all lend credence to the notion that students with intellectual and developmental disabilities do better academically in a supportive learning environment. A conducive learning environment has a heavy effect on the functional ability of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD), as highlighted in this study. Focusing appropriately on the adaptive behavior and self-help capacities of students with intellectual and developmental disabilities is crucial. The obligation of a functional performance in their daily life. There is a dire need to concentrate properly on the adaptive behavior and self-help skills of individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities.

The responsibility of a special education teacher is to create an environment that must be accessible, safe, and conducive for children with intellectual and developmental

disabilities. A conducive environment isn't just to provide a safe environment but also to provide facilities that fulfill their needs and improve the quality of life. The classroom design supports active engagement of children with IDD that builds peer interaction and social skills. The classroom must have a positive and supportive atmosphere, and adequate physical space is important for children with IDD to move around and engage in activities. The study is concluded on the point that the crucial role of a conducive learning environment in increasing the academic performance and overall development of individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities. A supportive classroom must promote adaptive behavior, self-help skills, peer interaction, and social engagement in addition to safety and accessibility. Teachers are responsible for developing routines that are both organized and flexible enough to accommodate a range of requirements through lesson planning, individualized education programs (IEPs), and flexible instructional practices. By ensuring enough physical space, positive teacher-student connections, and reinforcement-based techniques, educators can develop environments that empower children with IDD to thrive academically and socially.

Beyond academic outcomes, the study underlines that a friendly environment is multidimensional. It includes structured routines that offer predictability, physical arrangements that facilitate mobility, and reinforcement techniques that promote engagement. Positive teacher-student interactions remain at the center of this process, as they generate trust and motivation. Moreover, peer contact promoted through classroom design adds to the development of social skills, which are crucial for long-term inclusion in society.

Ultimately, a conducive learning environment is one that not only fulfills educational goals but also increases the quality of life, independence, and participation of those with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD).

6. Recommendations

The recommendations of the study, in light of the findings of this research, are mentioned below:

1. Special education teachers should design and adapt classroom environments to ensure that children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs) can actively participate in all learning activities.
2. Special education departments should provide structured and regular training in differentiated instruction to special education teachers, enabling them to effectively address the diverse learning needs of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs).
3. Special education teachers of the IDD field should implement applied behavior support strategies in their classrooms to proactively address the behavioral needs of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs).
4. The special education department should provide continuous professional development opportunities and training facilities, including appropriate resources for teachers working in remote areas, enabling them to develop the skills necessary to create conducive learning environments for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs).

5. Special education teachers of the IDD field, in collaboration with government agencies and local stakeholders, should establish structured platforms such as workshops and seminars to strengthen parent–teacher partnerships for the welfare and well-being of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs).
6. Future researchers should explore the development of conducive learning environments for children with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDDs) using alternative research designs.

7. References

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